

THE USE OF MULTIMEDIA TOOLS IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation. The article discusses the effective use of multimedia tools in She language classes, multimedia technology and the requirements for creating assignments and their presentation. The opinions of scientists and Methodists are analyzed.

Keywords: virtual world, cyberpedagogy, multimedia technology, animation, video, active approach.

In recent years, the concepts of "information explosion" and "virtual world" have appeared in speech activity. The concepts of cyber-reading, cyber-chat, cyber-pronunciation, and cyber-communication are getting absorbed into it. Even the concept of cyberpedagogy has entered science. These should be considered as factors that can have a negative effect on the streams we are used to seeing and hearing. Here, in addition to accurate and correct reading of words, beautiful and error-free writing, their ability to enter various forms and appearances is of particular importance. In this case, the ability to influence their layers of meaning through the means of expressive reading of sounds, words, phrases and sentences is clearly visible. As a result, the relevant skills and competencies of the student are realized in a faster, more convenient and more pleasant way.

As A. Gartsov pointed out, "each pedagogical period creates a generation of unique technologies" [1]. Gradually, the place of verbal theoretical education was replaced by visual education. "Later, it was determined that the demonstration training was not acceptable, and the training based on the activity approach came in its place" [2]. The effectiveness of the implementation of the training based on the activity approach in connection with the intuition, feeling, attention, memory, imagination, thinking, speech, mental and spiritual processes of human activity was recognized in the rapidly developing multimedia tools in the information age. When working with multimedia tools, the reader directly observes zharaenny himself, experiences it and draws his own conclusions. When traditional lessons and multimedia lessons are compared, the advantages are obvious: in traditional She language textbooks, the text of the materials related to the topic is presented, and in most cases, pictures are presented in a static way; In classes with multimedia participation, there is a possibility of sharing the text of the material, the voice or video that explains it, several pictures, diagrams, graphs, animation, music related to the topic. "In the process of working with the textbook, if students' skills of independent reading, learning or re-remembering rules, identifying and consolidating grammatical phenomena based on exercise tasks are developed, in the process of working with multimedia applications, the desire of students to learn increases, their interaction with peers improves, independent mastery of a new topic and will have the opportunity to self-evaluate" [3]. At the same time, diversity in multimedia media interests the student, encourages thinking, expands the worldview, connects

knowledge, skills and experience. A scientist, a science teacher, and a computer expert need to come together to create the perfect multimedia lesson plan. In addition, the goals and requirements for creating e-learning resources should be kept in mind. To create multimedia technologies, it is necessary to take into account pedagogical, psychophysiological and methods requirements. Compliance of the product created to the educational requirements of the state educational standards, current educational programs; psychophysiological requirements should be developed in a simple, precise, understandable and funny way, taking into account the age, worldview, and interests of the student; and according to the requirements of methods, the educational material to be studied should be developed in a logical sequence, ensuring coherence, taking into account the complexity of the mastered knowledge level, on the basis of various methods. In addition, if it is compared with technician, esthetician, didactician and other requirements, scientific, comprehensible, continuity and integrity are ensured, the topic is systematically covered, interactivity of communication, the overall unity of teaching, education, and development is taken into account, a positive result is achieved in accordance with requirements and expression.

Neglecting the multimedia conditions when creating multimedia technologies for use in She language classes can also lead to the failure of the prepared lesson from the didactic point of view. Unfortunately, many teachers do not pay attention to the small details when using multimedia tools. In order to use the projector, the windows of the classroom should not be covered with curtains, on the contrary, it is important to place the projector or interactive board in a zone where the light does not fall and pay special attention to the colors in it. If the classroom is not equipped for multimedia lessons, it is appropriate to conduct multimedia lessons in informatics classrooms.

The innovation approach based on these requirements serves as an effective factor for students to gain new experience, to understand original and critical thinking, to develop a desire for the future, and to educate a person with an independent intellect. Another possibility is that multimedia developments can be used in classroom activities, in activities for working with gifted students, in activities for working with low learners, in language courses, as well as for independent work at home. It is only necessary for the teacher to determine the speed of mastering the educational material, the amount of material, the level of difficulty and, most importantly, to form the skills and culture of the student to use the necessary media. Scientists emphasize that it is possible to achieve a number of positive factors through the use of multimedia technologies in education.

Selecting and sorting practical tools for using multimedia tools in She language education, writing multimedia scripts based on the purpose of the lesson is done directly by the teachers of science. Cooperation with programming specialists is established to turn Oz's ideas into products. The technological process of creating multimedia technology is carried out according to the following: first, a script is written based on the idea. Individual information on the topic (presentations, text, tables, images, diagrams, diagrams, audio recordings) is prepared. Everything is combined in one folder and given technological processing (animation movements, rank, sound). A multimedia content is created and stored (see Figure 1).

1.1.2-расм. Мультимедиа воситаларининг она тили дарсларида жорий қилиниши.

Issues of expanding the use of information technologies in education of the She language are among the priority tasks of the state education system. But most of the She language teachers understand the use of computer capabilities only as the use of text editors and Power Point programs. In fact, there are several programs that serve to improve the quality of education, and She language teachers are not aware of the benefits of such programs [3]. Usually, science teachers do such projects with computer programmers. Computer programmers may have sufficient knowledge and experience in the quality of the product to be created, but they cannot fully meet the requirements of the methods. Therefore, teachers of the modern She language should acquire not only their specialties, but also the ability to create multimedia products using the Beams program.

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